

Assessing the Implementation of Senior Secondary School Health Science Education Curriculum in South-East Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study investigated the implementation of the Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum in South-East Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses were used for the study. A Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population of this study consisted 1,154 Health Science teachers in 1,283 senior secondary schools across the five states of South-East Nigeria (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States). Stratified random sampling technique was used for the selection of 736 samples. The research instrument that was used in this study was a 25 items self-structured questionnaire titled. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation. This was done by three (3) experts, one (1) from Measurement and Evaluation unit, and two (2) from Department of Curriculum and Instruction unit, all of the Faculty of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. Reliability index was determined by the use of Cronbach Alpha reliability statistics tool which yielded 0.84. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum and a significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education and School Administrators should provide teachers with opportunities for professional development to enhance their academic qualifications and pedagogical practices. Also, Ministry of Education, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), and School Administrators should develop a curriculum implementation plan that outlines specific goals and objectives for urban and rural schools.

Keywords: Perception, implementation, Senior Secondary, Health Education, Curriculum

Introduction

Education plays a pivotal role in shaping individuals and preparing them for active participation in their communities, making it a fundamental cornerstone of societal development. For decades, it has served as a societal process for capacity building and upkeep. The national policy on education acknowledges education as a tool for achieving effective national development (Akubuilu, Ugo, Ugo, Ugochukwu, & Ikehi, 2019). Also, O'Connor in Obasi, Kanno & Obih (2017) examined education as a deliberate societal process for transmitting cultural heritage to successive generations through educational institutions such as schools, colleges, and tertiary establishments. They further emphasized that education possesses the potential to instigate shifts in behaviour and character, while also enhancing capabilities for targeted development, particularly within the realm of health science education.

Background to the Study

The Health Science Subject is included in both junior and senior secondary curricula to equip students with the knowledge necessary for leading a productive and healthy life within the society, while also accommodating varying talents and opportunities in the future. (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). As a branch of applied science, Health Science focuses on matters related to the

well-being of both humans and animals. Health Science encompasses the study, research, and comprehension of health, with the application of this knowledge aimed at enhancing well-being, combating diseases, and gaining insights into the functioning of both human and animal bodies. (Ajibola, 2017). Moronkola (2017) defines Health Science as a multidisciplinary domain that encompasses a wide spectrum of scientific, medical, and health-related subjects. It entails the investigation of the human body, including its functions, ailments, remedies, and the overarching promotion of health and well-being (Moronkola, 2017).

The significance of Health Science in a child's education is apparent, as a fulfilling life revolves around individual health, which forms the core of health education objectives. According to Moronkola (2017), health education in school stems from the universal quest for improved and more enjoyable living. The goal of the subject (Health Science) is to provide students with knowledge on employing health promotion and protection strategies to prevent disease outbreaks and assist individuals in enhancing their health (Moronkola, 2017). The objectives of health education as summarized by Adebayo and Owoaje, (2016); Ajibola,(2017) are to inform and educate people on the need for a healthful life for quality living that will facilitate productivity, encourage people to change negative attitude and practices to positive ones that promote personal and community health; encourage people to be aware and use available health care services; make people see the need to prevent diseases rather than spending more time and money to treat them, encourage people to continue in their local ways that promote health.

Research conducted by Moronkola, (2017) and Nwonye and Ayomah, (2018) highlighted that health instruction in secondary schools across various regions in Nigeria was inadequately conducted. The study identified the lack of implementation of essential components in the health education curriculum, along with issues such as insufficient infrastructure and instructional materials, as the primary reasons behind the substandard state of health education in the Nigerian school system. It is crucial to note that regardless of the role one occupies, good health is of paramount importance. Without good health, productivity will be severely compromised. Previous research by Putnam (2014) indicated that the approved health education curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools was implemented under the name "health Science"

The curriculum is meticulously designed with the target audience in mind, aiming to facilitate effective learning through the suitable implementation of means and methods. According to Obasi et al. (2017), teaching is the central implementation activity of the curriculum for any subjects. The term curriculum implementation is often referred holistically as all aspects of educational experience within the reach of the students in the school (Akubuilu, Ugo, Ugo, Ugochukwu & Ikeh, 2019). Akubuilu et al. (2019) also, emphasized that the curriculum represents the deliberate interaction between students and the tools, content, materials, resources, and evaluation processes designed to achieve educational objectives. The current Health Education curriculum in Nigeria consists of ten instructional units that secondary schools are expected to implement (Nafisatu & Aminu, 2021). These ten units are: Growth and development, Food and nutrition, Physical health, Safety and accident prevention, Prevention and control of communicable diseases, Community and environmental health, Family life and sex education, Emotional and social health, Chemicals which alter behavior, and Consumer health (Source: Federal Ministry of Education, 2014). The ten units in the Health Education curriculum are designed to address the physical, mental, emotional, and social aspects of school children's health both in theory and practice. Proper implementation of these units has the potential to motivate students to maintain and enhance their health, prevent diseases, and decrease risky behaviours.

Adamu and Adole (2017) observed that a society's educational goals are put into action through the curriculum, which serves as a pivotal aspect of the educational process. Curriculum is not merely a sub-system within education; it is, in fact, the most critical component of any educational undertaking (Nafisatu and Aminu, 2021).Ronaldah (2020) asserted that no matter how well the curriculum of any subject is planned, designed and documented, if not properly implemented the curriculum may not achieve its goal and objectives. Steve (2018) viewed curriculum implementation as the process of putting the curriculum into work for the achievement of the goals for which the curriculum is designed. Achieving the objectives of health science in Nigerian schools heavily relies on the effective implementation and teaching of health science concepts.

Teacher quality and qualifications have great impact on curriculum implementation. Professional and academic qualifications of teacher are two vital concepts which cannot be separated in an attempt to analyze the effectiveness of the teacher in curriculum implementation. The National Policy on Education (NPE) has prescribed a minimum of National Certificate in Education (NCE) as the basic qualification for junior secondary school teachers in Nigeria (FRN, 2013). This is to ensure that those who go into the teaching profession have the basic educational qualification and teaching background. Their expertise ensures that health science education is delivered in a way that is accurate, engaging, and inclusive, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes for all students.

Teaching involves a teacher, a learner, subject matter, and teaching materials. The importance of the quality and competence of Health Education teachers cannot be overstated. Ajibade (2019) asserts that "no educational system may rise above the quality of its teachers". In the implementation of any curriculum development, teachers are the most crucial factor. Health Science teachers are expected to have a thorough understanding of health science concepts. Comprehensive knowledge of the subject enables teacher to effectively explain and simplify the concepts for students (Agugoesi, et al., 2022).

The competence of a Health Science teacher largely hinges on their knowledge of health education issues and concepts. to a large extent, depends on his knowledge of civic issues and concepts. Adebule and Akomolafe (2014) states that a teacher cannot effectively teach a concept they are not well-versed in. If a teacher lacks thorough knowledge of the subject matter, they cannot be an authority in the classroom. Adeyemi (2018) and Akubuilo et al. (2019) argue that the presence of qualified teachers significantly influences students' performance and attitudes both in school and in society. Achieving the objectives of health science in Nigerian schools heavily relies on the effective implementation and teaching of health science concepts. Despite the acknowledge importance of health education in shaping the well-being of students and the broader community, there is limited comprehensive research on the actual extent of implementation of the Health Science curriculum in senior secondary schools in the South East region of Nigeria.

Furthermore, there is a shortage of qualified teachers to implement the Health Science curriculum. Also, insufficient information exists on the extent to which the prescribed Health Science curriculum content is being covered in schools, leaving a gap in understanding how comprehensively the curriculum is delivered. Hence the need for the present study on the extent of the implementation of senior secondary school Health Science curriculum in South East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The successful execution of an educational curriculum plays a pivotal role in achieving the goals of that educational programme. Many commendable programs encounter challenges during implementation, causing excellent curriculum plans and educational policies to falter and

sometimes fail completely. Regardless of how meticulously a curriculum is planned, designed, and developed, its implementation holds paramount importance. Moreover, examining the implementation process can highlight best practices and innovative strategies that can be scaled up or replicated in other regions. Furthermore, if the subject is not implemented correctly and fails to engage learners' interest, the intended goals of Health Science may remain unattainable, even if the curriculum itself is considered adequate in terms of its objectives. It is indeed essential to explore the extent of Health Science curriculum implementation in South-East Nigeria, as there appears to be a shortage of literature on studies conducted within this specific region. Based on the information presented, the research problem to be addressed presented in a question form is: "What is the level of implementation of senior secondary school Health Science Curriculum in South-East Nigeria?"

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the implementation of the Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum in South-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to address the following objectives, to:

1. find out the extent teachers' academic qualification affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria
2. Determine the extent to which the Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the conduct of this study.

1. To what extent do teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria?
2. To what extent have Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents been covered in South East Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated to guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 alpha level.

- H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum.
- H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria.

Methods

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. Creswell (2014) stated that descriptive survey involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes, depicts, and describes the data collected without any manipulation. The population of this study consists of all 1,154 Health Science teachers in 1,283 senior secondary schools across the five states of South-East Nigeria (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States). The sample size for this study was 736 Health Science teachers in which 221 teachers from Abia, 262 teachers from Imo and 253 teachers from Enugu states. The teachers were proportionally drawn from the total population using a stratified proportionate random sampling technique to ensure fair representation of gender and location. In terms of gender distribution, 380 teachers are male, while 356 are female. For location, 386 teachers are from urban schools, while 350 teachers are from rural schools. The instrument that was used for data collection is a researcher-made structured closed-ended questionnaire for teachers and

principals; Appendix A shows the teacher questionnaire (TQ). The teacher questionnaire is made up of twenty-five (25) items, divided into two (2) sections (A & B). Section A (3 items) sought demographic data about the respondents; such as teachers' gender, qualifications, and year of experience. The remaining 22 items made up section B, was further divided into 2 clusters based on the two research questions that guided the study. Cluster 1 contain eight items with information on teachers' academic qualification and curriculum implementation, cluster two, with 14 items sought information on the content coverage. The instrument (questionnaire) was rated on 4-point scale consisting of four different degrees (levels) of response: Very High Extent VHE (4), High Extent HE (3), Less Extent LE (2), and Very Less Extent VLE (1), and Strongly Agree SA (4), Agree A (3), Disagree D (2) and Strongly Disagree SD (1) respectively.

The instruments were subjected to face and content validation. This was done by three (3) experts, one (1) from Measurement and Evaluation unit, and two (2) from Department of Curriculum and Instruction unit, all of the Faculty of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. The validated instrument was trial-tested using thirty secondary school teachers. The scores obtained from this trial testing were also used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Using the Cronbach's Alpha, an internal consistency estimate of 0.84 for the instrument was obtained. The instrument was administered with the help of ten (10) trained research assistants who were briefed on how to administer, direct and collect the questionnaire from teachers on the spot. This approach aimed to ensure immediate collection of the instrument upon completion, resulting in a high return rate of 95% for the questionnaire. The analysis of data collected for the study was carried out using descriptive statistics -frequency and simple percentage for all research questions, except research question one which was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The researchers also uphold their dedication to ethical standards. In carrying out this study, the researchers ensured adherence to ethical guidelines. Permission was obtained from the appropriate authorities, respecting the perspectives of the respondents. Participants were given clear and detailed information to facilitate informed and voluntary participation. Additionally, data protection measures were put in place to safeguard the confidentiality and integrity of the collected information.

Results

The results from the data analysis were presented in the tables below:

Research Question 1: To what extent do teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria. The results for answering research question 1 were presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Mean Score on extent teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum.

S/N		Male		Female		Overall		Decision
		N= 380		N= 356		N = 736		
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
1	Teachers with NCE have the ability to implement health Education	3.18	.636	2.83	.782	3.01	.731	HE
2	Teacher with Sc. Ed in Health Education are in better position to implement Health Education	3.22	.649	3.10	.793	3.16	.724	HE
3	Teachers with B. A and PGDE have the ability to implement Health Education	2.79	.963	2.54	.766	2.67	.882	HE
4	Teachers with academic qualification of B. A in other areas can implement Health Education better	2.47	.940	2.24	.720	2.36	.848	LE
5	Teachers with B. Ed in related areas are better prepared to implement Health Education curriculum	2.69	.811	2.71	.784	2.70	.797	HE
6	Teachers with B. Ed in Health Education are poised to teach Health Education	3.69	.528	3.53	.563	3.61	.550	HE
7	Teachers with master in education in Health Education are poised to implement Health Education better	3.81	.466	3.67	.599	3.74	.539	HE
8	Teachers with Ph. D in Health Education are better equipped to implement Health Education	3.87	.417	3.76	.425	3.82	.424	HE
Cluster Mean		3.22	0.68	3.05	0.68	3.13	0.69	HE

Table 4.1 showed that the cluster mean of the items 1 - 8 was 3.22 for male teachers and 3.05 for female teachers with the overall cluster mean score of 3.13. This is above the mean bench mark of 2.50 on a 4-point rating scale. This implies that that teachers’ mean scores on the extent teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria is high. The Table also revealed that the cluster standard deviation of the items 1 – 8 was .68 for male teachers and .68 for female teachers with the overall standard deviation of .69. This also shows that the respondents were not far from the mean opinion of one another, in their responses on the extent teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria. This added further validity to the mean. A corresponding hypothesis that addressed the above research question is:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum.

Table 4.2: t-test Analysis on Mean Ratings of Male and Female teachers on the extent to which teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum.

Teachers	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-cal	P-value	Remarks
Male	380	3.22	.676	734	3.0484	.000	S
Female	356	3.05	.679				

Data in Table 4.2 show a P-value of .000 which is less than the alpha value of .05. This means that the null hypotheses that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers’ academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum.

Research Question 2

To what extent have Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents been covered in South East Nigeria? The results for answering research question 1 were presented in the Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Mean Scores on the extent of coverage of Health Education curriculum in Secondary Schools in South East Nigeria.

S/N	Rural N= 350		Urban N= 386		Overall N = 736		Decision
	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
	1 Human growth and development	3.35	.539	3.05	.549	3.19	
2 Food and Nutrition	3.29	.673	3.17	.535	3.23	.607	HE
3 Physical health	3.33	.636	3.14	.709	3.23	.682	HE
4 Safety and accident	2.80	.749	2.94	.709	2.87	.731	HE
5 Prevention and control of communicable diseases	3.17	.671	2.94	.678	3.05	.683	HE
6 Community health	3.07	.664	2.97	.823	3.02	.753	HE
7 Environmental health	2.89	.784	2.95	.758	2.92	.771	HE
8 Family life education	2.86	.799	2.95	.512	2.90	.665	HE
9 Sex education	2.55	.940	2.55	.694	2.55	.820	HE
10 Emotional health	2.70	.956	2.38	.681	2.53	.839	HE
11 Social health	2.99	.813	2.67	.662	2.82	.754	HE
12 Chemicals which alter behavior	2.64	.784	2.18	.738	2.40	.794	LE
13 Consumer health	2.83	.887	2.79	.672	2.81	.781	HE
14 Consumer education	2.73	.947	2.87	.638	2.81	.802	HE
Cluster Mean	2.94	0.77	2.83	0.67	2.88	0.73	HE

Table 4.3 showed that the cluster mean of the items 1 - 14 was 2.94 for rural school teachers and 2.83 for urban school teachers with the overall cluster mean score of 2.88. This is above the mean

bench mark of 2.50 on a 4-point rating scale. This implies that teachers' mean scores on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria is high. The Table also revealed that the cluster standard deviation of the items 1 – 14 was 0.77 for rural school teachers and 0.67 for urban school teachers with the overall standard deviation of 0.73. This also shows that the respondents were not far from the mean opinion of one another, in their responses on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria. This added further validity to the mean.

A corresponding hypothesis that addressed the above research question is:

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.4: t-test Analysis on the extent of coverage of Health Education curriculum in Secondary Schools in South East Nigeria.

Teachers	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-cal	P-value	Remarks
Rural	350	2.94	0.77	734	2.0580	.04	S
Urban	386	2.83	0.67				

Data in Table 4.4 show a P-value of .04 which is lesser than the alpha value of .05. This means that the null hypotheses which state that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

The discussion of the findings was organized in line with the research questions;

The findings of that study revealed that the respondents to a high extent agreed that teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum in secondary schools in South East Nigeria. Whereas the corresponding hypothesis indicated that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in secondary schools on the extent to which teachers' academic qualifications affect their ability to implement Health Education curriculum. This is in line with the findings of Akubuilu et al. (2019) on the extent of implementation of social studies in secondary schools in Enugu State which revealed that academic qualifications of teachers influenced teacher's ability to implement social studies curriculum to a great extent.

The finding of the second research question revealed that the respondents agreed to a high extent that Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria. Whereas the corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural teachers on the extent Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum contents have been covered in South East Nigeria. This supported Agugoesi, et al. (2022) on Evaluation of teachers' implementation of curriculum content areas in junior secondary schools' science subject which revealed a high extent coverage of Basic Science Curriculum content areas.

Conclusion

The study investigated the extent of the implementation of senior secondary school Health Education curriculum in South-East Nigeria. The researcher concludes that teachers' academic qualifications impact their ability to implement the Health Education curriculum in South East Nigerian secondary schools. There are significant differences (in favour of male teachers) in male and female teachers' views on this impact. Despite challenges, the Senior Secondary School Health Education curriculum has been covered in South East Nigeria. However, Urban and rural teachers differ in their views on curriculum coverage and resource utilization. Health Education teachers adopt recommended teaching methods, but there are significant differences (in favour of female teachers) in male and female teachers' adoption of these methods. Several challenges, including scarcity of resources and poor teacher incentives, hinder effective implementation of the Health Education curriculum. Strategies like adequate funding, provision of classroom spaces, and relevant textbooks can address these challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made;

1. Ministry of Education and School Administrators should provide teachers with opportunities for professional development to enhance their academic qualifications and pedagogical practices
2. Ministry of Education, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), and School Administrators should develop a curriculum implementation plan that outlines specific goals and objectives for urban and rural schools.
3. Ministry of Education, State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), and Local Government Education Authorities should conduct a needs assessment to identify gaps in instructional resources and provide additional support to rural schools.
4. Ministry of Education, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), and School Administrators should provide teachers with training and support on effective teaching methods and encourage sharing of best practices.

Disclosure Statement

This research study is conducted with the utmost commitment to transparency and ethical standards, with no conflicts of interest.

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